

GST: IT'S IMPACT ON ECONOMIC GROWTH WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO DEVELOPED AND DEVELOPING COUNTRIES

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ABSTRACT

GST (Goods and Service Tax) will be a game changer for the Indian economy by creating a common market and reducing the cascading effect of tax on the cost of goods and services. In our study we have analysed the impact of GST on economic growth of developed and developing nations. The study shows positive relationship between GST and economic growth. There is a significant impact of GST on economic growth in developing countries however there is less impact of GST in case of developed countries. This study is based on secondary data.

Keywords: GST, Economic growth, Economy, Cascading.

INTRODUCTION:

Tax systems play an important role in the economic progress of a country. A good tax system should keep in view issues of income distribution and also try to generate expenditure on public services and infrastructure development. Initially VAT was introduced in Indian taxation system. VAT is a significant improvement over the local tax system. It is a multipoint tax system where there will be no duplication of tax. Despite the success of VAT, there are certain limitations both at central and at the state level. To solve the issues untouched by VAT Finance Minister Pranab Mukherjee presented the budget on July 06, 2009 and said that GST will be effective from April 2010. However, after the gap of 7 years GST is finally going to be implemented from April, 2017.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

A recent study by Nantob (2014) who implemented the dynamic panel data GMM estimator revealed that tax structure including GST had negative impact on the level of economic growth.

A study by Bolton and Dollery (2004) concluded that the GST was highly successful in generating the tax revenue and economic growth in developed countries such as Australia, Canada and New Zealand.

A study done by Gold (1991) concluded that an economic growth of a country relies on the changes on each of tax structure. These studies proved that, any single component of tax structure like GST will lead to give the different impact on economic growth for each country.

A study of the impact of the GST on international trade has been conducted by Desai and Hines (2005) found that openness and export performance are significantly and negatively related on the presence of GST.

Guptha (2014) in her study stated that implementation of GST in the Indian framework will lead to commercial benefits which were untouched by the VAT system and would essentially lead to economic development.

Venkadasalam (2014) has analyzed the post effect of the goods and service tax (GST) on the national growth on ASEAN States using Least Squares Dummy Variable Model (LSDVM) in his research paper. He suggested that the household final consumption expenditure and general government consumption expenditure are positively significantly related to the gross domestic product as required and support the economic theories.

The relationship between tax structure and economic indicators has been conducted by Gober and Burns (1997) mentioned that any changes in each type of taxes may lead to different impact on a country's economy.

Using the dynamic panel data analysis and divided the countries into five groups of countries (low, lower middle, upper middle, high income and OECD countries), Hakim et al. (2013) argued that there is a mixed results between GST on economic growth in all groups of countries. He concluded that GST have significant and negatively correlated with the movement of economic growth in low, lower middle and upper middle income (developing) countries.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM:

GST is the biggest tax reform in decades throughout the world, but India has taken little steps to implement goods and service taxes on April 1, 2017. Implementation of GST will create more economic activities which directly stimulate the manufacturing of goods and services resulting in economic growth of a nation. However now question arises

- (a) Will GST be an efficient way in stimulating revenue and economic growth of developing and developed nations?

OBJECTIVES:

The objectives of the study are:

- (a) To examine the relationship between GST and economic growth indicators
- (b) To study the impact of GST on economic growth

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

(a) Sources of Data:

For the study secondary data have been taken. The required data are collected from World Bank Development Indicators (WBDI).

(b) Sample Design:

The study consists of 20 developed and 30 developing countries and data set includes both developed and developing countries, totaling 50 countries. We collected top developing and developed countries according to GDP per capita. We found 50 developed countries and 75 developing countries who adopted GST from World Bank site. Then, we took 40% of developed and developing countries for our study.

(c) Tools:

The statistical techniques used for analysis are correlation to analyze the relationship between GST and GDP, Multiple regression analysis to analyze the impact of taxes on income, taxes on goods and services, taxes on international trade and control; variables like population growth, inflation, foreign direct investment, government expenditure on gross domestic product per capita growth. Multicollinearity test has been conducted to determine the extent of relationship among the independent variables.

1. Dependent Variables

a) GDPPC - Gross domestic product per capita growth

2. Independent Variables

a) PIT - Taxes on income, profits (% of revenue)

b) INTERT - Taxes on international trade (% of revenue)

c) GST - Taxes on goods and services (% of revenue)

3. Control Variables

a) POP - Population growth (Annual population growth rate)

b) INF - Inflation (Consumer Price Index)

c) INVEST - Foreign direct investment (% of GDP)

d) GOV - Government expenditure (% of GDP)

GOODS AND SERVICE TAX (GST):

Currently there are multiple indirect taxes such as excise duty, service tax, VAT etc. GST seeks to eliminate multiplicity of taxes, rates, exemptions to achieve uniformity of taxes across the country. It would provide greater certainty and transparency of taxes. India will adopt dual GST model and taxes levied on each kind of transaction.

- SGST - State GST, Collected by State Govt.
- CGST - Central GST, Collected by Central Govt.
- IGST - Integrated GST, Collected by the Central Govt.

Under the new system SGST & CGST, a transaction sale within the state shall have two taxes, SGST - which goes to the state and CGST - which goes to the centre. A transaction of sale from one state to another shall have only one type of tax, the IGST - Which goes to the centre.

DATA ANALYSIS:

After collection of data it is necessary to analyze and interpret data for final result and findings. Here, researcher has used GDPPC, PIT, INTERT, GST to find out the impact of GST on economic growth. All the calculation are carried out by using Microsoft excel 2007 and NCSS 11 and SPSS V20 software.

Dependent Variables:

a) GDPPC - Gross domestic product per capita growth

Independent Variables:

a) PIT - Taxes on income, profits (% of revenue)

b) INTERT - Taxes on international trade (% of revenue)

c) GST - Taxes on goods and services (% of revenue)

Table No: 1 Summary statistics of tax structure and economic indicators in 20 developed countries (2005-2014)

Variable	Unit of Measurement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
GDPPC	Annual percentage growth Rate of GDP per capita based	1.26	0.25	-12.92	12.93
PIT	% of revenue	28.80	1.10	7.07	66.47
INTERT	% of revenue	0.75	0.06	-0.03	6.18
GST	% of revenue	30.12	9.90	2.43	55.46
Inflation	Consumer Price Index (Annual Percentage Change)	2.52	0.16	-1.35	15.43
Population Growth	Annual population growth rate	0.57	0.06	-2.08	6.35
Invest	% of GDP	5.07	1.06	-79.73	142.41
Govt. Expenditure	% of GDP	18.77	0.25	9.95	26.48

Source: Self Compiled

Table No: 2 Summary statistics of tax structure and economic indicators in 30 developing countries (2005-2014)

Variable	Unit of Measurement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
GDPPC	Annual percentage growth Rate of GDP per capita based	3.54	0.22	-14.42	18.48
PIT	% of revenue	25.59	0.82	1.37	62.79
INTERT	% of revenue	8.49	0.45	-15.84	33.98
GST	% of revenue	31.55	0.74	1.78	77.33
Inflation	Consumer Price Index (Annual Percentage Change)	7.44	0.35	-8.28	59.21
Population Growth	Annual population growth rate	1.21	0.05	-1.31	3.75
Invest	% of GDP	3.35	0.17	-5.97	18.34
Govt. Expenditure	% of GDP	15.04	0.23	5.03	25.87

Source: Self Compiled

The data sets are summarized in table no 2 and 3. The average value of GDPPC is 3.54 percent per annum, with the standard deviation of 0.22 in developing countries, while the GDP per capita growth and standard deviation in developed countries are 1.26 percent per annum and 0.25. Among three different types of taxes, GST can be considered as the highest contributor where the mean value reported is between 30 to 31 percent in both developing and developed countries. The percentage of tax on income was stated 25.59 percent in developing countries and 28.80 percent in developed countries. However, the percentage of international trade tax was stated different among these countries, where 8.49 percent of revenue in developing countries as against only 0.75 percent of revenue in developed countries.

CORRELATION AND REGRESSION ANALYSIS (DEVELOPED COUNTRIES):

$$Y_e = \beta_0 + \beta_1PIT + \beta_2INTERT + \beta_3GST + \beta_4INF + \beta_5POP + \beta_6INVEST + \beta_7GOV + \epsilon$$

Where,

- Y_e = GDPPC
- β₀ = Constant or the value of Y when all values of X are zero
- β₁, β₂,..... = Slope of the independent variables
- PIT = Taxes on income, profits
- INTERT = Taxes on international trade
- GST = Taxes on goods and services
- INF = Inflation
- POP = Population Growth
- INVEST = Foreign Direct Investment (Inflow)
- GOV = Government Expenditure

Table No 3: Impact of PIT, INTERT and GST of Developed Nations on GDPPC

	β Coefficients	Standard Error	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Intercept	-0.04952	1.408828	0.036233	0.021482
PIT	-0.01735	0.023383		
INTERT	0.401795	0.305361		
GST	0.050363	0.031767		
Inflation	0.302994	0.104258		
Population Growth	-0.2294	0.279741		
Invest	0.03039	0.016039		
Government Expenditure	-0.25843	0.074383		

Source: Self Compiled

From the multiple regression model given above β represents slope or coefficient which implies dependent variable will change with change in independent variable and intercept explains value of dependent variable if all independent variables (PIT, INTERT, and GST) are absent. The independent variables along with their β coefficient are detailed below.

From the regression statistics as given above, it is found that there is a positive relationship between GDPPC and PIT, INTERT, GST as evident from R² i.e.0.036233. It indicates 4% approx of GDPPC contributed by all the independent variables. It can be said that change in one unit of independent variables leads to 4% change in GDPPC.

PIT

Table no 5 shows that β coefficient of PIT is negative i.e. -0.01735. This advocates that PIT has a insignificant relation with GDPPC. It means if PIT will increase then GDPPC will decrease. It states that PIT is not a major tax for developing nation's growth. An income tax is a tax imposed on individuals or entities (taxpayers) that vary with the income or profits (taxable income) of the taxpayer. But in developed countries income tax is not contributing significantly towards GDP growth.

INTERT

The β coefficient of INTERT is positive i.e. 0.401795. It means there is a significant relation between INTERT and GDPPC. So tax on international trade is contributing 40 % towards developed nation's GDPPC. International trade is the exchange of capital goods and services across international borders or territories. In most countries trade on tax represents a significant share of gross domestic product.

GST

Table no 5 shows that β coefficient of GST is positive i.e. 0.050363. This advocates that there is significant relationship between GST and GDPPC. In developed nations goods and service tax influencing around 5% towards GDPPC. If GST will provide higher revenue, the government of developed countries can utilize it properly to boost productivity, economic growth and reduce national debt.

CORRELATION AND REGRESSION ANALYSIS (DEVELOPING COUNTRIES):

$$Y_e = \beta_0 + \beta_1PIT + \beta_2INTERT + \beta_3GST + \beta_4INF + \beta_5POP + \beta_6INVEST + \beta_7GOV + \epsilon$$

Where,

- Y_e = GDPPC
- β_0 = Constant or the value of Y when all values of X are zero
- β_1, β_2, \dots = Slope of the independent variables
- PIT = Taxes on income, profits
- INTERT = Taxes on international trade
- GST = Taxes on goods and services
- INF = Inflation
- POP = Population Growth
- INVEST = Foreign Direct Investment (Inflow)
- GOV = Government Expenditure

Table No 4: Impact of PIT, INTERT, GST of Developing Nations on GDPPC

	β Coefficients	Standard Error	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Intercept	4.65774	0.915152	0.033834	0.024042
PIT	-0.04943	0.016319		
INTERT	-0.00379	0.029998		
GST	0.005934	0.017871		
Inflation	-0.00078	0.038426		

	β Coefficients	Standard Error	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Population Growth	-0.15083	0.283563		
Invest	-0.12806	0.082558		
Government Expenditure	-0.03054	0.058454		

Source: Self Compiled

Table No 7 shows regression statistics result. It indicates that there is a positive relationship between GDPPC and PIT, INTERT, GST i.e. R2 is 0.033834. It indicates 3% approx of GDPPC contributed by all the independent variables. It means 1% change in independent variables leads to a change of 3% in GDPPC.

PIT

The β coefficient of PIT is negative i.e. -0.04943. This advocates that PIT has a negative relation with GDPPC. It means if PIT will increase then GDPPC will decrease. So the developing nations should use other taxes or incomes to boost their economy. In developing countries taxes on income or profit is not satisfactory for economic growth and to boost productivity.

INTERT

Table no 7 shows that β coefficient of INTERT is negative i.e. -0.00379. It means INTERT has a negative relation with GDPPC. The impact of INTERT is very negligible on GDPPC. So it is quite impossible to boost nation's economy. Taxes on international trade play a major role in economy growth, but in developing countries it is not significantly contributing towards growth.

GST

The β coefficient of GST is positive i.e. 0.005934. β coefficient states that there is significant positive relation between GST and GDPPC. The impact of GST in developing nation's GDPPC is very less. So the country should focus on productivity for growth of GDPPC. In developing countries GST is not providing higher revenue, so it creates hurdles in economy growth. The developing countries should depend more on foreign direct investment, trade openness to boost productivity and economy growth.

FINDINGS:

- There is positive relationship between GST and Economic Growth Indicators.
- There is no significant impact of GST on economic growth of developed countries; however it stimulates the commercial activities leading to economic growth.
- There is a significant impact of implementation of GST on economic growth of developing countries.

SUGGESTION:

- Like IFRS we should have a single understandable and simple tax structure for creating a global business friendly environment in the era of globalization.
- Reforms in allied regulatory frameworks in line with global standard should be brought in to make GST in India effectively operative.

CONCLUSION:

The study examines the effects of goods and service tax on economic growth among developing and developed countries. The main objective of this study is to investigate the impact of GST on economic growth of developing and developed countries. The result suggests that GST has positive impact on economic growth of developing and developed countries under the study. The government of India has decided to implement GST with effect from 1st April, 2017. This will boost the economic growth of the country as evident from the study.

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